

A Critical Study Of The Impact Of Covid-19 Pandemic On The Public Health Law In India

Deepthi Meena

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 09, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 11, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Pandemic, public health laws, emergency, Epidemic Diseases Act, Disaster Management Act, 2005</p>	<p><i>The novel coronavirus has been highly distressing for most countries globally, challenging the global structure of laws adhering to public health laws and any form of a medical emergency. India had comprehensive yet archaic forms of laws that were inadequate in tackling the pandemic. It was an uncertain and unfortunate crisis brought on the world. Thus, India was forced to look at the public health system and the legislations governing the same in-depth and bring about effective changes against them. We have seen the Indian legislative frameworks concerning the emergent medical laws more expansive and equip themselves with various facets of the earlier problems, which were hardly premeditated. However, today, enforcing newer legislation has allowed the dimensions of the public health law to emerge and enlarge, owing to its inherent flexibility. However, this paper also discusses the deficiencies and inadequacies from a holistic viewpoint that only reflects India's stance on the entire public health system.</i></p>
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Introduction

The ongoing pandemic had taken the world by its knee, and the world at large was in dire crisis. The uncertainty and ambiguity of the pandemic had caught most global governments off guard and in distress, which led to more effective means of adaptability and innovation. The public health sector felt a massive brunt, and in turn, the need to re-think the current legislative structure governing public health arose. India's strategy in tackling the pandemic was largely reliant on archaic laws that governed the public health sector. At the very advent of the pandemic, the Epidemic Diseases Act, 1897 came to rescue, which allowed the Government to announce curfews. In alignment with the Disaster Management Act, 2005, the Central Government resorted to announcing a nationwide lockdown, which was considered the most effective measure to curb the spread of the virus. This unknown threat had consumed the world at large and tested all and one. Especially, the entire legislative structure felt inadequate and was challenged to a greater extent. On 25th March 2020, the archaic quarantine laws as incorporated within the Indian Penal Code, 1860, and Criminal Procedure Code were used, but parallelly the ineffectiveness of the laws were equally visible in India alone and over 45 Lakhs globally. A year later, the anticipated second wave, in May 2021, had also left a prominent effect on the world, and currently, as anticipated, the third wave is doing rounds and still remain in the dark as proportionate and full proof measures are still under consideration. However, the fatalities and cases registered are far lower than the previous two waves.

However, this was a concerning medical emergency requiring governmental intervention in its most acceptable and stringent form. The legislative impediments that followed in dealing with this medical emergency are the primary issue of the paper. The need to have equipped laws that allow the Government to take measures in order to curb the mortality rate, but the pandemic brought to light the loopholes and inadequacies Indian legislation was faced with despite having pre-existing laws. The need to have the expansive structure of public health laws arose and this paper shall throw light on the same.

Indian Legislative Framework governing Public Health

The Indian Constitution, being the mother instrument, has developed the most powerful provision providing the fundamental right to life enshrined under Article 21, which has gone through elaborate interpretations and expanding the limit of the same to a great extent. Therefore, any crisis to health has not been shunned away from the article, which is largely reflective in the prominent cases like; *Paschim Banga Khet Mazdoor Samity versus State of West Bengal 1996 Mohinder Singh Chawla vs. The State of Punjab and Ors.* Where the right to health has been considered a crucial aspect of life. The Directive Principles within the Indian Constitution have also enshrined the provisions dealing with safe and secure health without any form of discrimination. The Indian Constitution has also incorporated provisions that allow both the Central and the States to make emergent laws concerning the seventh schedule and List III. The need arises in times of rapid spread of diseases that could pose

a risk to life. Therefore, both the State and the Centre has a massive role in protecting citizens under unprecedented circumstances.

The primary legislation that was resorted to were the Indian Penal Code, 1860, Epidemic Diseases Act, 1897, Livestock Importation Act, 1898, Indian Ports Act, 1908, Drugs and Cosmetics Act, 1940, Essential Services Maintenance Act, 1968, Indian Aircraft (Public Health) Rules, 2015 and Consumer (Protection) Act, 2019.

Epidemic Diseases Act, 1897

The legislation on public health is incidental and is not necessarily equipped to deal with any particular form of hazard but deals with conditions concerning deaths, birth, containment, mitigation of diseases outbreaks, etc. Other legislations like Indian Red Cross Society Act, 1920, Drugs (Control) Act, 1950, Consumer Protection Act, 1986, etc. The most significant legislations were the Epidemic Diseases Act, 1897, which is a short enactment that primarily focuses on preventing the spread of any life-threatening diseases but does not incorporate any provisions that allow the Government to intervene and take any form of extra-ordinary measure. This restraint could pose a hindrance in times of uncertainty and health crisis that are not premeditated. This Act also provides the authority to control the inflow of people or clusters of people by either banning travel or disallow the formation of any societal congregation. This Act is to be perused with the Indian Penal Code over various sections.

However, there are enough limitations in this Act that could pose detrimental to the effectiveness as it fails to take into account and clarify the basic meanings of the words "Dangerous" or "Infectious" or Epidemic for that matter. Mostly, the ideal extent that could allow the declaration of an epidemic is also uncertain. Therefore, the failure to outline an infectious disease's limits that could be liable for a health emergency is unclear. Followed by this, there is no clarification on the provisions that regularise and deal with the drugs to be disseminated or the "quarantine" procedures to be followed.

The Epidemic Diseases Act, 1897 empowers "any person" to execute power, whereas India already follows quite a strict approach in distributing power in a hierarchy. The primary health care workers are in close association with the DCMO; therefore, the incorporation of 'any person' could only result in a conflict.

The limitations of this Act were further overcome in the amended Act of Epidemic Diseases Amendment Act, 1937, where the Central Government was ensured enormous scope of power which allowed social removing, the conclusion of foundations, and impediment on movement to control COVID-19 in all states and Union domains in India under the Act. Accompanied with the Indian Penal Code, this Act also ensures strict actions are taken on infringement of the rules regarding quarantine and pestilence. The reading of the Epidemic Diseases Act, 1897 with the Indian Penal Code, 1860 under sections 188, 269, 270, 271 has revealed the issues relating to health and, if implemented, could be viable to withhold such dramatic changes which are in line with international legislation as well.

The International Health Regulations 2005 has also imposed several mandatory obligations to have complied with globally that deal with diseases that spread infections. It also overviews the general well-being and observes the health surveillance on a national scale through the provisions laid down in Articles 5, 6, and 7. World Health Organization had identified through the report published the numerous mechanisms and enactments that were readily available to battle any organic, compound, and radio-atomic perils at the degree of a section, control, and moderation

Disaster Management Act, 2005

The Disaster Management Act, 2005 played a crucial role in governing any issue related to disasters. The central Government relied on this Act to implement the nationwide lockdown initially as the ideal purpose of the Act is to ensure proper management of any disasters. This Act is responsible for establishing the NDMA (National Disaster Management Authority), SDMA (State Disaster Management Authority), And DDMA (District Disaster Management Authority). These bodies, after that, focus on the proper implementation of all restrictive measures, penalties in cases of infringement. The NDMA primarily deals with biological catastrophes and public health issues. The lockdown restricted all forms of mobility inter-state as well as intra- state, which was overseen by the National Defence and Military Act also. This Act empowers the Central Government to release any directive that can assist states in governing within their territories. In contrast to other relevant statutes, this Act serves the purpose of upholding and operating an exhaustive administration that creates awareness regarding any such disasters. Any form of violation of the provisions of the Act would amount to penalties as well as imprisonment of up to one year. This Act provides a protective blanket for officers that allow them to carry out their duties effectively. However, a significant question mark constantly looms around the definition regarding disasters under Section 2(d) of the Act. Even though Pandemics are not directly covered, but they can be placed under the heading of "grave concerns," given its magnitude, but whether this narrow interpretation suffices the Act in battling any such concerns in the future remains a question even now.

National Health Bill, 2009

Before the National Health Bill, 2009, the previously discussed Bill has primarily considered a softer form of law. The obligations that grew out of the Bill had tied member states to have a proactive change in the authoritarian position. The ultimate idea was to ensure a general form of humanity and well-being in times of

such constraints as the pandemic. The National Health Bill, 2009 supervises the aspects of insurance protection, upholds the fundamental right to health, equity and oversees justice. The administrative receptive to such health ideals are administered and powerfully constructed within the federal structure seamlessly. This Bill looks out for the smooth functioning of responses that are dealt with both at the state and national level front, including transparent provisions. This Bill does not explicitly looks to fulfill the standards of right-based health care, but it does provide sufficient space to accommodate provisions and the implementation of the same in a way that the human rights of people are not infringed even though they are kept in isolation. This aspect seems trivial but plays a more significant role in case the times of such a crisis seem to go beyond the anticipated time limit.

Epidemic Diseases ordinance, 2020

Another aspect of health care that deems appropriate is the debate concerning the safety of health care professionals. It is pertinent to ensure that the caregivers have a right to a safe and secure discharge of their duty along with protecting their personal property that has been seen to be a spot of target and damage during extreme aggression and agitation. The Health Services Personnel and Clinical Establishments (Prohibition of Violence and Damage to Property) Bill, 2019, looks into this aspect along with the Clinical Establishment and (Registration and Regulation) Act, 2010, which ensures the protection to property essentially. The frontline workers and doctors have seen to be at the forefront of such behavior many times, and to curb such disposal of harassment against such medical and paramedical forces; this Ordinance was passed by the President. This Ordinance enlarged the powers of the Central Government to take adequate measures and regulate all forms of laws to prohibit any form of discrepancy and violations thereafter. This initiative could stand as a measure to curb the allied pressures that are often subjected on the frontline workers as they receive the brunt of all aggression. Therefore, it was an adequate move from the legislative front.

The repercussions of a weak law: A critique

Lack of Transparency: Impeding the decision-making process

Emergent situations require emergent measures, especially with the current pandemic. The legislations were definitely a rescue. Still, the crisis was such that it had pointed out multiple loopholes within the existing systems. The spread of covid was an unwarranted threat, but the most considerable unforeseen circumstances were the allied issues faced by India for the first time. Therefore, the need to immediately acknowledge the concerns was the need of the hour. For example, the pandemic had contributed to the loss of privacy and often violated the right to one's property, one's liberty, privacy, etc. Therefore, the need to have transparent laws and regulations was indeed required. The caveats published should have been widely distributed in case that stepped on to individual rights and allows smooth decision-making process by all the stakeholders involved in broadcast sectors dealing with the health emergency. Still, unfortunately, that wasn't the case. The lack of transparency interfered with many aspects of individual rights. The Public Health (Prevention, Control, and Management of epidemics, bio-terrorism, and disasters) Bill, 2017, was introduced to rectify this gap. The Bill would also intervene in empowering and ensuring a more robust set of guidelines for all the levels of Government, especially the local government. However, such has still not seen the light of the day yet.

Threat to equality

India primarily relied on Section 144 of the Indian Penal code to enforce curfews in the hope of restricting the spread of the disease despite having the assistance of the Disaster Management Act, 2005. Section 144, as much as it smells of an archaic influence, also has brutal repercussions on any violation, which was not the ideal call-in times of mass panic and uncertainty that spread amongst people. The need to impose Section 144 would not arise, like many commonwealth countries, if only India had a progressive, all-encompassing, comprehensive set of legislation. The need to impose Section 144 to curb a virus seems arbitrary and uncalled for in the first place.

Naturally, the questions regarding justice and equality are of grave concern. The human rights aspect was a vast area that was conveniently overlooked, and many people were at the mercy of the rules and restrictions passed. The onset of the pandemic was reflected through the announced lockdown in March 2020 by the Government, and the first step to tackle the situation was repulsive to the protective measures that were ideally undertaken due to the large gathering of migrant workers intending to go back home. Many deaths on that front were due to a narrow-sighted order passed by the Central Government. Therefore, from the very inception, there was a lack of far-sightedness.

As and when the world proceeded to live within the pandemic and accommodated itself to the continuing times, the questions regarding accessible health care and equal distribution of facilities were challenged at many stages. Especially since the national legislation dealing with Epidemic failed on that front. With concerns regarding healthcare, the allied impediments like access to transport or receiving free healthcare, immediate availability of any form of services to patients likely to suspect covid, etc., were not complied with completely.

Discriminatory approach

The much anticipated second wave had taken India aback with its unpredictable nature and challenged the course of action planned by the Central Government concerning vaccination. As the first round of vaccination began with adults from 18 years of age onwards, there was no cap on the price discrimination that was differed from centre to state. The press release revealed the Government's discriminatory strategy, allowing the states to get into the price battle with private to get vaccines from the public sector. The Centre will likely pay a lower price for those same vaccines and ultimately abandoned its original plan to provide free immunizations to everyone amid a raging pandemic. The Supreme Court further materialized the concern as it took a *suo moto* action through the petition [In Re: Distribution of Essential Supplies and Services During Pandemic](#) as the discriminatory set of pricing defied the ultimate plan of serving the public at large and was not dependent on an individual's capacity by any means. This move was also violative of Article 14 as it lacked any intelligible differentia. Therefore, the need to account for the 'global good' was at stake. Another aspect that needs to be accounted for in line with discrimination would be the protection offered to officers *acting in good faith* under Section 73 of Disaster Management Act, 2005 and Section 4 of the Epidemic Diseases Act, 1897. However, the frontline workers, especially the doctors, were held responsible under many legislations, primarily the Consumer Protection Act, Clinical Establishment Act, Indian Medical Council Act, etc., in many instances, without considering their valuable role in challenging circumstances evidenced uncalculated priorities.

A comparative study of the legislation:

There have been many attempts at passing comprehensive legislation catering to the public health system; unfortunately, the states have vocally objected against the bills owing to their subject matter jurisdiction. Even though Madhya Pradesh and Tamil Nadu have their respective laws, a comprehensive and uncomplicated legislative framework is due. Many other countries like Canada have passed the Public Health Agency Act, 2006 and Public Emergency Act and Quarantine Acts are all efforts that look into dealing with '*chronic disease*' and measures to prevent the spread of such a disease. Singapore was considered very quick and effective in bringing about legislation the COVID-19 (Temporary Measures) Act 2020 (CTMA), which was temporary but was sufficiently comprehensive. The National Health Security Act, 2007 of Australia proved successful in tackling any "*national emergencies*." whereas, Public Health (Control of Disease) Act of 1984 passed in England looked into the overall protection along with sufficient surveillance. These various legislations are easily a reflection of how national legislation can effectively bring about a uniform law that is strong and that does not necessarily require a federal structure of governance when the country at large is combatting the same enemy.

Conclusion

The challenges of the pandemic on public health law could be considered a boon in the sense that it awakened the dormant and ineffective legislation, which otherwise would remain as a weak link. The paper attempted to be drawn by the task force in 2012 was seen to be a little jolt on the public health system to strengthen the same by evaluating the weaknesses and suggesting effective alternatives. The previously discussed regulations and laws are evidence of how the archaic public health laws have been upgraded, and comprehensive reforms have been brought about in times of grave crises like the Covid-19 pandemic. This also ensures the ability and flexibility of the legislative framework and the long-term need to bring about reforms and sufficient developments in the public health laws. The Ordinance, as reformed, makes it way more stringent to avoid petty violations by aligning the Act more on the criminal side rather than a civilian approach. Even though we still are fighting the battle and many uncertainties might come up in the future, it has given us an awakening call. The criticisms and violations have been effective in comprehending the status of India concerning the public health laws, and a comparative study well establishes the need to have a better and more stringent framework. It is undeniable that there is a definitive need to have an accessible, equitable, and largely seamless process. The strict architecture of care disposing mechanism has created a sense of hindrance in tackling this unwarranted issue. Therefore, India is standing at a stage where all the sectors and aspects of an operational framework have been challenged. This must be considered an opportunity to grow, develop, and challenge oneself in squeezing out the best possible version of the public health system.

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Author Information

Ms. Deepti Meena,

Research Scholar, Amity University, Rajasthan

Abhishek Baplawat

Assistant Professor, Amity Law School, Amity University Rajasthan
